

Charged Lepton Flavour Violation searches at LHCb

Giulia Frau ^{*1}

¹The University of Manchester, UK

On behalf of the LHCb Collaboration

Abstract

Charged lepton flavour violation (cLFV) is forbidden in the Standard Model at experimentally accessible levels, and therefore constitutes a sensitive probe for physics beyond it. Recently, the LHCb experiment has performed dedicated searches for cLFV processes, both in semileptonic b -hadron decays and in purely leptonic τ decays, setting competitive bounds on several decay modes. These results provide relevant constraints on a variety of new physics scenarios. With the larger datasets currently being collected and the upgraded detector, LHCb is expected to further improve the sensitivity to cLFV processes in τ decays, extending the reach in searches for possible signals of new physics.

1 Introduction

Lepton flavour represents an accidental symmetry of the Standard Model (SM) arising from the absence of right-handed neutrinos. The observation of neutrino oscillations [1], which provides clear evidence of lepton flavour violation (LFV) in the neutral sector, implies that LFV could in principle also occur in processes involving charged leptons (cLFV). In minimal extensions of the SM that introduce right-handed neutrinos, however, the expected cLFV rates remain suppressed to unobservable levels due to the small neutrino masses and GIM-like cancellations. By contrast, many new-physics (NP) scenarios predict lepton flavour to be naturally violated in the charged sector with rates potentially within reach of current experimental sensitivities [2, 3].

In this proceeding, I present a review of the most recent searches for cLFV decays conducted with the LHCb experiment, including the search for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}\tau^\pm\mu^\mp$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\tau^\pm\mu^\mp$ decays, the search for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}\tau^\pm e^\mp$ decay, and the $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decay. The analyses discussed are based on LHCb data collected during Run 1 (2011–2012) and Run 2 (2016–2018) in pp collisions at centre-of-mass energies of 7, 8 and 13 TeV, depending on the decay channel under study.

2 Search for the $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decay

Thanks to its excellent muon identification system and high-precision vertexing, LHCb is an ideal experiment to search for $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays, offering an exceptionally clean reconstruction of the three-muon final state [4, 5]. A first search, conducted on Run 1 data, led to a limit of $4.6(5.6) \times 10^{-8}$ at 90% (95%) CL [6] on the branching fraction of the decay. As of today, the most stringent limit coming from a single experiment is 1.9×10^{-8} at 90% CL, set by the Belle II experiment on data collected in electron-positron collisions [7]. Recently, also CMS contributed to the field, establishing a limit of $2.9(3.6) \times 10^{-8}$ at 90% (95%) CL using

*Presenting author.

Run 2 data [8]. In this context, I present the preliminary result of the search for $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays using data collected at the LHCb experiment in Run 2 [9] and corresponding to a total integrated luminosity of 5.2 fb^{-1} .

Compared to Belle II, LHCb benefits from a much larger τ production, primarily originating from heavy-hadron decays, including $D_{(s)}$ mesons produced either promptly or in b -hadron decays, as well as by direct decays of b -hadrons. The $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ branching fraction is evaluated relative to the known branching fraction of a normalisation channel, chosen to be the $D_s^- \rightarrow \phi(1020)(\mu^- \mu^+) \pi^-$ decay. Given the similar topology and kinematics, the $D_s^- \rightarrow \phi(\mu^- \mu^+) \pi^-$ channel is also used to calibrate the simulation of $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ events.

The suppression of the main background components is achieved by means of two multivariate classifiers. The first one, C_{AC} , based on kinematic and topological information, and on variables describing the isolation of the decay products, is trained for the suppression of the combinatorial background, arising from the random combination of three charged tracks coming from the same decay vertex. The second one, C_{PID} , based on kinematic and particle identification information, is trained for the suppression of background coming from hadrons misidentified as muons. Another important source of background comes from the $D_s^- \rightarrow \eta^{(\prime)}(\mu^- \mu^+ \gamma) \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu$ channel. Its contribution is suppressed by applying the requirement $M(\mu^- \mu^+) > 450 \text{ MeV}/c^2$. In order to increase the sensitivity to the signal decay, the evaluation of the limit on the branching fraction of the $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decay, is performed in 15 regions of the output of the two classifiers mentioned above. A simultaneous maximum-likelihood fit is performed in these regions to extract the signal yield in the signal region. The result of the fit in the most sensitive bin is shown in Fig. 1 for 2018 data.

Given that no significant excess of signal events is measured, a preliminary upper limit is placed on the branching fraction of the $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decay using the CL_s method [10] at $2.4 (2.8) \times 10^{-8}$ at 90% (95%) CL. The expected and observed CL_s distributions are shown in Fig. 1 as a function of the assumed branching-fraction values.

Figure 1: On the left, result of the fit to the mass spectrum of the three muons in the most sensitive C_{AC} and C_{PID} region for 2018 data. On the right, CL_s distribution as a function of the assumed branching fraction for $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays. The horizontal red line corresponds to the 90% confidence level.

3 Search for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ decays

Various searches for LFV B -meson decays with $\tau\mu$ final states have been conducted by the Babar, Belle and LHCb collaborations [11–14]. This proceeding discusses the first searches for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ [15] and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ [16] decays using data collected by the LHCb experiment during Run 1 and Run 2, corresponding to a total integrated luminosity of 9 fb^{-1} .

For the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ channel, two independent analyses are performed for the two possible lepton–charge configurations, due to their different background compositions and the distinct possible theoretical interpretations of the results [17]. The K^{*0} in the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$

decay is reconstructed via the $K^{*0} \rightarrow \pi^- K^+$ decay, while in the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ channel the ϕ resonance is reconstructed through its $\phi \rightarrow K^- K^+$ decay. In both channels, the τ lepton is reconstructed through its $\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^- \nu_\tau$ or $\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^0 \nu_\tau$ decay. The $B^0 \rightarrow D^-(\pi^- K^+ \pi^-) D_s^+(K^+ K^- \pi^+)$ is used as the normalisation channel for the evaluation of the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ branching fraction, whereas the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \psi(2S)(J/\psi \pi^- \pi^+) \phi(K^- K^+)$ decay is adopted for the corresponding normalisation in the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ analysis.

The reconstruction of the B^0 and B_s^0 meson masses is challenging due to the presence of a neutrino and possibly of a π^0 in the final state, which are not reconstructed. Two different techniques are employed for the reconstruction of the B^0 and B_s^0 meson mass in the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ analyses, respectively. The former exploits the component of the missing momentum carried by the neutral particles perpendicular to the B^0 direction, p_\perp , by evaluating the corrected mass as $m_{corr} = \sqrt{p_\perp^2 + m_{K^* \tau \mu}^2} + p_\perp$. The latter, instead, performs a kinematic fit of the decay chain with constraints on the decay topology and mass values of the particles involved [18]. An extended unbinned maximum-likelihood fit is performed to the corrected $B_{(s)}^0$ mass to extract the signal yield, and the result is reported in Fig. 2. Since no significant excess of signal events is found, upper limits are set on the branching fraction of the decays. The limit on the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ branching fraction, $1.0(1.1) \times 10^{-5}$ at 90% (95%) CL, represents the first limit on the decay and it is competitive with other $\tau\mu$ searches. Similarly, the limits on the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ \mu^-$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^- \mu^+$ decays, namely $1.0(1.2) \times 10^{-5}$ at 90% (95%) CL and $8.2(9.8) \times 10^{-6}$ at 90% (95%) CL, provide competitive constraints on $b \rightarrow s \tau \mu$ transitions, and are consistent with recent limits from Belle [12].

Figure 2: Result of the fit to the corrected mass of the B^0 meson for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ \mu^-$ (top left) and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^- \mu^+$ (top right) channels, respectively, and of the B_s^0 meson for the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ channel (bottom).

4 Search for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm e^\mp$ decay

Previous searches for cLFV B decays with τe final states have been conducted by the BaBar and Belle collaborations [11, 12]. The analysis here discussed represents the first search for such

decays at LHCb, specifically for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm e^\mp$ decay [19]. The search is carried out on Run 2 data, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 5.4 fb^{-1} . For the same reasons outlined in Sec. 3 for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ channel, two separate analyses are performed on the two possible charge configuration of the leptons in the final state. Similarly to the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ analysis, the K^{*0} is reconstructed via the $K^{*0} \rightarrow \pi^- K^+$ decay, and the τ lepton through its $\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^- \nu_\tau$ or $\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^0 \nu_\tau$ decay. The $B^0 \rightarrow D^-(\pi^- K^+ \pi^-) D_s^+(K^+ K^- \pi^+)$ decay is used as the normalisation channel in the branching fraction evaluation as well as in the calibration of the simulation. An extended-maximum-likelihood fit is performed to the B^0 mass reconstructed through the kinematic fit discussed in Sec. 3 in the context of the $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$ analysis. The result of the fit is shown in Fig. 3 for the two possible charge configurations. No significant excess of signal events is found and upper limits are set on the branching fraction of the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^- e^+$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ e^-$ decays at $5.9 (7.1) \times 10^{-6}$ at 90% (95%) CL and $4.9 (5.9) \times 10^{-6}$ at 90% (95%) CL, respectively, providing the most stringent limits on LFV $b \rightarrow s \tau l$ transitions.

Figure 3: Result of the fit to the B^0 corrected mass for the $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^- e^+$ (top) and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^+ e^-$ (bottom) channels.

5 Conclusions

Searches for cLFV decays provide stringent constraints on potential contributions from NP models. LHCb continues to advance the sensitivity of such searches, delivering the world's most competitive limits on numerous branching fractions. The searches discussed in this document illustrate only a small fraction of the broader LHCb programme in this domain, which also includes searches for $b \rightarrow s e \mu$ transitions [20] as well as the first search for the $\tau \rightarrow \phi(K^- K^+) \mu^-$ decay ever attempted at a hadron collider. By the end of Run 4, LHCb is expected to collect a dataset about five times larger than that of Runs 1 and 2 combined, using a fully upgraded detector and a fully software trigger system [21]. This larger dataset will enhance the sensitivity to cLFV searches and allow the exploration of new phenomena.

References

- [1] SUPER-KAMIOKANDE collaboration, *Evidence for oscillation of atmospheric neutrinos*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **81** (1998) 1562 [hep-ex/9807003].
- [2] D. Bećirević, S. Fajfer, N. Košnik and O. Sumensari, *Leptoquark model to explain the B-physics anomalies, R_K and R_D* , *Phys. Rev. D* **94** (2016) 115021 [1608.08501].
- [3] A. Crivellin, L. Hofer, J. Matias, U. Nierste, S. Pokorski and J. Rosiek, *Lepton-flavour violating B decays in generic Z' models*, *Phys. Rev. D* **92** (2015) 054013 [1504.07928].
- [4] LHCb collaboration, *The LHCb Detector at the LHC*, *JINST* **3** (2008) S08005.
- [5] F. Archilli et al., *Performance of the Muon Identification at LHCb*, *JINST* **8** (2013) P10020 [1306.0249].
- [6] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton flavour violating decay $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$* , *JHEP* **02** (2015) 121 LHCb-PAPER-2014-052 CERN-PH-EP-2014-236, [1409.8548].
- [7] BELLE-II collaboration, *Search for lepton-flavor-violating $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays at Belle II*, *JHEP* **09** (2024) 062 [2405.07386].
- [8] CMS collaboration, *Search for the lepton flavor violating $\tau \rightarrow 3\mu$ decay in proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV*, *Phys. Lett.* **B853** (2024) 138633 [2312.02371].
- [9] LHCb collaboration, *Search for $\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays at the LHCb experiment with Run 2 data (LHCb-PAPER-2025-052, in preparation), to be submitted to JHEP* (2025) .
- [10] G. Cowan, K. Cranmer, E. Gross and O. Vitells, *Asymptotic formulae for likelihood-based tests of new physics*, *Eur. Phys. J.* **C71** (2011) 1554 [1007.1727].
- [11] BABAR collaboration, *A search for the decay modes $B^\pm \rightarrow h^\pm \tau^\pm l$* , *Phys. Rev. D* **86** (2012) 012004 [1204.2852].
- [12] BELLE collaboration, *Search for the Lepton Flavor Violating Decays $B^+ \rightarrow K^+ \tau^\pm l^\mp$ ($l = e, \mu$) at Belle*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **130** (2023) 261802 [2212.04128].
- [13] BELLE, BELLE-II collaboration, *Search for lepton flavor-violating decay modes $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm l^\mp$ ($l = e, \mu$) with hadronic B-tagging at Belle and Belle II*, *JHEP* **08** (2025) 184 [2505.08418].
- [14] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton flavour violating decay $B^+ \rightarrow K^+ \mu^- \tau^+$ using B_s^{*0} decays*, *JHEP* **06** (2020) 129 [2003.04352].
- [15] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton-flavour violating decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \tau^\pm \mu^\mp$* , *JHEP* **06** (2023) 143 [2209.09846].
- [16] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton-flavor violating decay $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi \mu^\pm \tau^\mp$* , *Phys. Rev.* **D110** (2024) 7 LHCb-PAPER-2024-006, CERN-EP-2024-114, [2405.13103].
- [17] M. Bordone, O. Catà and T. Feldmann, *Effective Theory Approach to New Physics with Flavour: General Framework and a Leptoquark Example*, *JHEP* **01** (2020) 067 [1910.02641].
- [18] W.D. Hulsbergen, *Decay chain fitting with a Kalman filter*, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* **552** (2005) 566–575.

- [19] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton-flavour-violating decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}\tau^\pm e^\mp$* , *JHEP* **11** (2025) 172 [2506.15347].
- [20] LHCb collaboration, *Search for the lepton-flavour violating decays $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}\mu^\pm e^\mp$ and $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\mu^\pm e^\mp$* , *JHEP* **06** (2023) 073 [2207.04005].
- [21] LHCb collaboration, *LHCb Trigger and Online Upgrade Technical Design Report*, CERN-LHCC-2014-016, LHCb-TDR-016.